

Stirling Power - for a sustainable future

Introduction

A Stirling Engine is an external combustion engine that can run on any external heat source, as long as the source is hot enough. Stirling Engines can run on anything from a blowtorch to the rays of the sun. The Stirling Engine can utilize the effect of an internal regenerative heat exchanger, thus enabling the thermal efficiency of the engine to approach the maximum achievable efficiency, the Carnot efficiency. The Stirling Engine has the capability to produce power from both bio-fuels and focused sun rays, thus making it a viable green technology.

Usability

The Stirling Engine's greatest advantage lies in the different sorts of power plants or thermal power stations which it can be used in. Due to the high theoretical and practical thermal efficiency and the numerous sorts of fuels applicable for the engine, the advantages are plentiful. The Stirling Engine is very flexible and useful, especially in parts of the world with unreliable infrastructure and lack of fossil and carbon based fuels, due to the relative scalability of the engine, and the relative independence of infrastructure.

Furthermore, the principles and construction of the engine is rather simple in contrast to modern gas turbines and diesel engines.

Technologies for Green Powering

The Stirling engine can run on many different heat sources. We have tried using solar energy, which is an abundant resource. We have utilized a Fresnel lens, which concentrates the rays of the sun. In a sun rich environment, like Africa, this is an applicable and reliable energy source.

Using organic biofuels is also a viable solution. We have implemented biofuels as a heat source by utilizing a homemade stove, made from simple materials, which does not require a much manufacturing. With the stove operational, the Stirling engine runs very well, and at the same time, household heating is possible. The diversity of fuel possibilities which can be used for the Stirling Engine is tremendous, since it can run on practically anything which can generate heat. This is a huge advantage in different places of the world.

Kilde: <http://www.stirling.dk>

Kilde: <http://www.pilleborsen.dk/catalog/images/DSC00055.JPG>

Kilde: http://s.nijl.edu/competition/2009/Cat2_2_Winner_Group142/img/solar_thermal_web.jpg

Future Possibilities for the Stirling Engine

When summing together all of the options and ways of applying and using fuel for the Stirling engine, the possibilities for future development is widespread. The use of the engine as a thermal power station is a good way of implementing Stirling technology. Building this system into a 40 foot container and then shipping it to a developing country for electricity production, and water heating is certainly possible. If a country is hit by devastating natural disasters, e.g. earthquakes, electricity and hot water is quickly applied by these quick response containers. The only demands for the operation of these containers are combustible materials and some water to cool the engine, to make district heating possible for households.

"World Energy Program"

Kilde: <http://helmetster.files.wordpress.com/2009/03/emma-maersk-underway.jpeg>
http://subairshow.aero/images/press_imgs/en.jpg

Type of Stirling Engine

This project has focused its attention on the Gamma version of a Stirling Engine. A gamma-type Stirling engine consists of two different pistons, the displacer piston and the power piston, in two different cylinders, connected to the same crankshaft. The hot cylinder, which contains the displacer piston, is connected to the cold cylinder by a tube. Upon applying heat on the displacer cylinder, the displacer piston will move away and circulation of air will commence. The different phase positions of the temperature and piston positions is displayed below.

District Heating Possibilities

Since we have chosen to cool our Stirling Engine with running water, the opportunity of district heating is possible. In this way the overall performance of the engine is increased, because the temperature in the cold area can be controlled. When applying the district heating principle to our project, it is now possible to build a thermal power station. The circulating water is heated by the engine, and the water temperature that the end-user receives can be varied with different technical solutions.

When applying this principle and making use of the heat that otherwise would disappear into the air, the total efficiency of the process is furthermore increased, so the energy in the fuel is used in the best possible way.

Ideal for Teaching Purposes

The design of this engine is based upon the following criteria:

- Hands on possibilities for changing important characteristics of the engine, e.g. phase angle, heat source, compression ratio and so on.
- A great deal of interactivity, so future engineering students can see and understand the principles of the Stirling engine.
- Widespread use of clear materials if possible. We did not want to encapsulate the engine in a box.

The project gives the possibility for future engineers to get hands on experience with tomorrows technology.

Project title "Solar Powered Stirling Engine"

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